

Dialogues and Reflections on the importance of social media during the educative process

Maria Appelroth^{1,*}, Karin Bolldén^{2,+}, Cristina Carburaru^{3,†}, Leonardo Espinosa Leal^{1,**}, Gavin van Niekerk^{4,++}, Hafizah Osman^{3,*§}, Victoria Owen^{4,*+}, and Kari Trost^{5,+§}

¹Arcada University of Applied Sciences, Helsinki, Finland.

²Luleå University of Technology, Luleå, Sweden.

³National University of Singapore, Singapore.

⁴IIE Varsity College, South Africa.

⁵Stockholm University, Sweden.

* e-mail: maria.appelroth@arcada.fi

+ e-mail: karin.bollden@ltu.se

§ e-mail: cristinacarbunaru@gmail.com

** e-mail: leonardo.espinosaleal@arcada.fi

++ e-mail: gvanniekerk@varsitycollege.co.za

*§ e-mail: hafizahosman@nus.edu.sg

*+ e-mail: vix.owen09@gmail.com

+§ e-mail: kari.trost@buv.su.se

ABSTRACT

In this report we present the conclusion of the discussions about the role of social media in educational processes. We discuss the importance of using social media as a complementary tool during teaching not only as a pedagogical tool but also as a mean to train the students in digital literacies.

Introduction

Modern society has embraced social media. From economical to sentimental relationships, social media plays an important role as both, communication and exposition channel. Apart of the possible controversies regarding safety and trust, still it is undeniable the advantages that using these in the digitized world. However, the business of social media relies in the capacity of keeping the users engaged as long as possible and overall, that they share as much personal information as possible. Therefore, the question to answer is not if teachers should use social media as a pedagogical tool, but how they should use them. In this report, we present the reflections in form of dialogues from different perspectives (background and geographical) about the issues and possible solutions to the use of social media during the teaching process. We try to address and discuss about the digital capabilities of both staff and students when they engage in social media as mean to improve the pedagogical practice and then, we explore the academic literature to find a practical guidance for both, find tools or information about the topic, and then if is it possible to create a checklist to measure the level of digital literacies of students and staff.

Discussion and Results

Karin Bolldén: In order to discuss with both teachers and students regarding what to share or not to share online, I embarked on a mission to find some literature that could serve as support in that process. I found the work by *Dabbagh & Kitsantas*¹. The authors presents a pedagogical framework that teachers could use in order to scaffold students' learning when using Personal Learning Environments (PLEs). "A key feature of a PLE is that the learner develops and online identity where the personalized learning environment provides cues . . . that prompt the learner about what to share, what not to share, who they choose to share with" (*Dabbagh & Kitsantas*, p5)¹. Perhaps this article could be used as a support for teachers when designing courses that contain activities with the purpose of supporting students designing and managing their online presence/activities for professional purposes? The visitor-resident map could be used as a base for uncovering the status of each student's PLN, serving as a communicative resource in group discussions. A way of measuring the development of students (and/or teachers) PLN/digital capabilities could be to revise/rewrite the map on a regular basis. In the end of a programme/course, you could ask them to put the first map alongside the latest one, and ask them to reflect, discuss and document how it has evolved over time,

and the reasons behind that development. When discussing each others maps, it is possible to highlight questions of privacy, what to share and with whom, critical thinking when using a particular platform (for example what information Facebook shares to third party). One thing with the content in the article concerns me though. In the model the teacher should encourage students to use ICT, such as blogs, wikis, google calendar, youtube, flickr, linkedin, delicious and so on. Due to GDPR², I am wondering how far we as an institution can go, regarding encouragement of using social media in teaching and learning. Could it be part of an exam assignment in a university course, or only an optional/voluntary activity? As the discussion goes at my university in Sweden, it is only the later alternative that is possible. Have you other experiences?

Leonardo Espinosa: In many journal articles and websites are stated the pedagogical benefits of using online channels or social media with the students³. However, there is a clear consensus that it is necessary to have some ground rules for teachers when they engage in social media with their pupils⁴. Some research has shown that students feel more confident if the teacher shows a high level of self-disclosure in social media⁵. Despite of that, most of the published results acknowledge the positive impact of using social media, those studies were done on limited cultural, social and geographical communities. More extended research using, for instance, meta-learning techniques is necessary to identify if socio-cultural differences are an important factor in the possible impact of social media, see a possible approach in *Greenhow et al.*⁶. The rule of thumb in more of the cases is "don't say anything on your social media profile that you wouldn't say in class."⁵. Other recommendations depend on the level of comfort that the teacher has when uses social media: 1. Use different accounts for working and for private life, 2. Be aware of the privacy issues that concern you and your students when sharing information online (eg. GDPR), 3. Teach students some basic ideas about social media safety, privacy, security, and digital literacy before engaging them in the use of these tools, 4. Be aware of the legal issues related to the use of social media. In this last recommendation, the importance of having an institutional framework is key and, more importantly, that everybody knows it. It is the responsibility of society to teach that being online doesn't mean being anonymous or disconnected from the duties of physical citizenship. In modern societies, the rules and laws are extended in the cyberspace. *Ignorantia legis neminem excusat*.

Kari Trost: I would like to add that standards and practices for sharing in pedagogy of social media use would be beneficial particularly since self disclosure can vary from individual to individual. Of the over 400 university students asked regarding social media and self disclosure, *Ampong et al.*⁷ reported that privacy risk was the strongest predictor of whether individuals shared information about themselves and perceived control significantly influenced variations in self disclosure online. It also comes down to ideas of social competence independent if its online or offline like Leonardo mentioned. Reich published a review of research up to 2014 on the topic of social competence online⁸. Lots exists on negative and bullying behaviors but little on social competence online. She however is clear to state that her findings do not suggest or support ideas that simply using your offline social competence practices online as a quick fix. On the contrary, it may be very different depending on forum, platform, etc. Therefore, she does seem to indirectly support, in my thinking, that having social competence guidelines for students before and during a class but also to help in their professional careers. And yes, these social competence guidelines would need to be specific to discipline and culture. This may even be particularly important in terms of how to phrase things online, using emojis, caps,!!, etc. I would be curious to hear what others would think of such guidelines. If anyone has come across a set of guidelines that are standardized, I would really like to look at that.

Cristina Carburaru: Leonardo's comments and observations can be a great starting point for my personal endeavor to share more and engage my students through online channels. Overall, I find that many of the online interactions help students to get to know the teacher (on a personal level), but do not help much in the process of learning. To engage with students to help them learn is much more challenging than just letting the students know some personal details about the teacher. Lots of work is needed, and the posts/interactions have to be carefully chosen. Kari's comments are very useful for the students' perspective on online interactions. I think a set of "rules" might not help much because students might feel that rules limit their freedom in the online space, they might just give up on engaging. I agree that guidelines should be made available to students, and they should be introduced at a very young age (10 years old, maybe) when the kids start their online footprint. There are a few programs focusing on cyber-wellness and privacy targeted to school kids. At some level, students might understand better than us, the teachers, the impact of their online interactions because they tend to take many decisions and learn more online than offline.

Kari Trost: Also, we talked about the cultural implications of sharing online via Facebook, LinkedIn etc. I like that cultural variation is lifted in our discussions but I would also like to lift the variations in disciplines. Other disciplines may have more rigid ethical practices regarding the private and personal and information sharing with *per se* clinical students, medical students, and so forth. A good read on this is by *Younggren and Gottlieb*⁹. Its a bit dated but it lifts interesting questions like... "Should I just avoid it to make my professional life easier?", "Can I really be the judge of oversharing or not since I/m a part of the dual relationship (dvs can I really judge if I'm oversharing too much)", Can the *sharing* disrupt the learner from learning (dvs: the focus is on me the teacher/professor/clinician instead of trying to learn, the concept being taught, or healing)". The idea being simply that sometimes not knowing about the device giving the delivery can help one focus on the actual package.

Gavin van Niekerk: As part of our discussion I raised the matter of employability and how educators need to consider this when engaging with their students. Current students will need to empower themselves with a range of skills as the existing

market demands of them. How employable are students in this 'digital age'? By understanding how they think we can use this to help shape what, when and how to engage with them. Which ENABLERS will encourage both teachers and students to be more engaging in an online space? While technology created specifically for learning; LMS, polling devices, ebooks, standard authoring tools, moocs and virtual classroom are but a few to mention one has to look at technologies adapted for learning e.g. blogging, social networks, mobile platforms and wikis (not an exhaustive list) and how we bring this into the classroom.

Cristina Carbanaru: I find that using tools and online technologies in class might not always help. Students tend to get a bit confused about what it is required for them to do. Again, we have to be careful about what tools we choose and what is the value that they bring to learning and teaching.

Gavin van Niekerk: What to share and not to share is a contentious one because what one person may consider to be private can be viewed as entertainment for another. Before sharing there needs to be a set of guidelines (collective agreement) on what is acceptable or not. In developing this collective agreement it empowers students within the process allowing a partnership to be formed between student and lecturer. Surprises could easily be dealt with by referring to the collective agreement in place. This will lend itself to forming a partnership that will both encourage and foster constructive engagement.

Kari Trost: I wanted to address your question Karin. In my dept, we use social media quite a bit for students to learn about each other. We also use digital assignments, etc. Blogs are used in teaching and in research but not to my knowledge in assignments. When students do use online materials like interviews, chatrooms, and announcements for like thematic analysis, etc for a thesis paper...our department requires ethical approval with our department ethics board). It works well to both avoid pitfalls and consider GDPR. For example, students often contact host of chatroom and notify members, members are anonymous and not to use their "chatnames" etc.

Maria Appelroth: I found myself concentrating more on the topic of digital literacies and capabilities of staff and students and how to develop that. Learners today are more diverse than ever before, with a wider range of educational and ICT experience. This means that the digital literacy needs to become more wide-ranged, more flexible and more proactive¹⁰. When incorporating digital tools into educational practices it should be the institution that validates particular aspects of digital literacy practices¹¹. In developing digital literacies the organizational culture plays a big role. Culture is complex and there can be a lot of subcultures inside an organization across departments, teams etc. 'The way we do things around here' might need to be changed and this requires skilled leadership.¹² "Support is most effectively integrated where there is an institution-wide policy of assessing and progressing learners' skills"¹⁰. To be able to incorporate developing of digital literacy it is in my view also important to have a clear idea of what digital literacy means for the institution. One description is the one *Beetham & Sharp* talk about in their framework. Digital literacy is "the functional access, skills and practices necessary to become a confident, agile adopter of range of technologies for personal, academic and professional use"¹¹.

It is the lecturers that design and deliver the curriculum, so for them to be able to support the students, their digital literacies should be developed and assessed¹¹. The key for institutions is to engage staff in change and create opportunities for development and conversation. To do so you can use frameworks and other models to visualize and engage. This should be done on an institutional level so that everybody is on the same page and has the same goals. It is important to have the right form of guidance for the staff in question. Lack of time is one of the biggest issues, so the guidance needs to be on-demand and highly accessible. The use of workshops and communities of practice to build partnerships and networks can help the use of digital literacies in the long run. Staff also need time, space and support to assess their own capabilities, anxieties and needs so that they can decide which tools are right for them¹². To get the staff to rethink their earlier practices it is important to support flexibility and innovation in curriculum design and to make learning development a concern for teaching staff¹⁰.

The developing of a professional digital identity can be a motivator to engage the staff with digital issues, since digital choices are aspects of personal identity¹². It can be a challenge to keep the boundaries between the personal and professional when using digital tools that make you always available. In one research where staff was interviewed, some saw the time used to learn a new digital tool as an investment to improve teaching and learning opportunities for their students as well as saving time later. Some just accepted that there will be some blurring of boundaries of home and work, some had clear strategies on managing those boundaries. They for example did not accept students as friends on Facebook or they were very specific on when and where they would be available for the students online¹¹.

In changing cultures of learning to place greater value on *literacies of the digital*, institutions must engage and motivate students to develop learning literacies. It is important to articulate the educational benefits and importance of digital literacies. Students' digital and learning literacies need to be assessed and supported as they engage in academic tasks and they need to learn skills like reflection and peer group support, so they can improve their learning strategies also in the future¹⁰. It's been suggested that attitudes and motivation and being a digitally confident learner, motivates students to try out new practices and acquire new skills in digital technology¹¹. Students need the time and support to assess their own individual capabilities and needs to be able to develop their own digital identity in different contexts. Ideally this should be offered at the start of a course and regularly as they progress. There are a range of self-assessment tools that can be used, reflection and action planning around this is very important¹².

Students need guidance and support to be able to handle the blurring boundaries of real and virtual, public and private and work and leisure. They also need to learn to navigate in a networked society, as well as handle the increase of digital technologies and rapid social and techno-social change. These should be a part of their learning goals. To support these capabilities we should design flexible learning opportunities, continually review how technologies are integrated into curriculum tasks, support learners to use technology and develop effective strategies for learning with technologies and use assessment and feedback to encourage innovation in learners' approaches to study¹⁰.

Students are generally more digitally confident and fluent than staff in the use of personal and social media. They do need support and guidance in how to apply this knowledge to the academic study but they are often more willing to explore different technologies and what that can bring to their learning¹². As a teacher it is important to be open and honest about our role as a teacher and build a collaborative trusting relationship with the students, and to develop our digital skills through exploring and seeking guidance¹¹. Diverse skills of staff and students should be recognized and used as resources, where students can be used in partnerships with staff and other students in projects developing digital literacies¹⁰.

Conclusion

Social media has impacted on our public and private space. How we separate this is key to developing a work life balance. Should we therefore have private and public accounts, or should we just accept the blurring of boundaries between home and work? The role of social media has become pivotal in how we teach and learn. Educators therefore need to address the question of not if but when to use technology and social media to engage with our learners. Before we can successfully engage online, we must establish the digital capabilities of staff and students. Thereafter it is important to identify clear guidelines for online interaction as well as creating an awareness of the legal issue relevant to online engagement. Research suggest that students are more digitally astute compared to their more mature educators and hence educators need to harness this intelligence for students to develop at their true potential. These digital capabilities may not be true for all students and where students lack the requisite skills educators must support students in acquiring these early on. We must however be aware that when developing others social competencies that it speaks to a specific discipline and is equally mindful of individual cultures. As educators we must address how employable our students will be. By understanding how they operate we can help shape our engagement with them. Educators must see students as partners in learning and grow together. How do we then encourage the use of social media in the learning process without it being disruptive? Today's students are more diverse therefore levels of interaction with them must reflect variety and flexibility. Hence, we must be supportive by encouraging students to develop a digital identity. Ultimately the use of technology in education for interaction and engagement must be under constant review in order to meet the ever-changing digital landscape.

References

1. Dabbagh, N. & Kitsantas, A. Personal learning environments, social media, and self-regulated learning: A natural formula for connecting formal and informal learning. *The Internet higher education* **15**, 3–8 (2012).
2. Council of European Union. Council regulation (EU) no 269/2014 (2014). <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1416170084502&uri=CELEX:32014R0269>.
3. The educator's guide to social media (2015). <https://www.connectsafely.org/eduguide/>.
4. Dos and don'ts for using social media as a teacher (2018). <https://education.cu-portland.edu/blog/leaders-link/educational-social-media-use/>.
5. Song, H., Kim, J. & Park, N. I know my professor: Teacher self-disclosure in online education and a mediating role of social presence. *Int. J. Human-Computer Interact.* **35**, 448–455 (2019).
6. Greenhow, C., Campbell, D., Galvin, S. & Askari, E. Social media in teacher professional development: A literature review. In *Society for Information Technology & Teacher Education International Conference*, 2256–2264 (Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE), 2018).
7. Ampong, G. *et al.* Examining self-disclosure on social networking sites: A flow theory and privacy perspective. *Behav. Sci.* **8**, 58 (2018).
8. Reich, S. M. Connecting offline social competence to online peer interactions. *Psychol. Pop. Media Cult.* **6**, 291 (2017).
9. Younggren, J. N. & Gottlieb, M. C. Managing risk when contemplating multiple relationships. *Prof. Psychol. Res. Pract.* **35**, 255 (2004).
10. Beetham, H., McGill, L. & Littlejohn, A. Thriving in the 21st century: Learning literacies for the digital age (Ildia project) - executive summary, conclusions and recommendations. (2009).

11. Bennett, E. Learning from the early adopters: developing the digital practitioner. *Res. Learn. Technol.* **22**, 21453 (2014).
12. UK Joint Information Systems Committees (JISC). Developing digital literacies (2014).
<https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/developing-digital-literacies>.